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An Empirical Survey of Individualized Consideration on Talent Management Practices: Lessons from Insurance Companies in Kenya

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine how individualized consideration relates to talent management practices. Using a convergent mixed methods design, the study population consisted of 2832 senior, middle, and lower management staff, with a sample size of 384 selected using a stratified proportionate random approach. Data was collected using a structured questionnaire and document analysis from insurance companies and academic journals. Statistical Package for the Social Sciences version 24 was used to analyse collected data. Descriptive statistics included frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations, while inferential statistics included multiple statistics such as Chi-square for independence, while correlations and regression analysis were carried out to test the study hypotheses. The study findings were presented in tables and figures. Qualitative data was analysed through the use of thematic analysis and presented in prose form. The study found a significant positive relationship between individualized consideration and talent management practices. The study recommends that insurance company management in Kenya and beyond emphasize individualized consideration in their leadership style to improve talent acquisition, development, engagement, and retention.

Keywords: Individualized Consideration, Talent Management, Insurance Companies

1. Introduction

The insurance market in Kenya is critical in the future-proofing of corporate and individual investments, health and livelihoods. This expectation requires the insurance industry to effectively deal with disruptive market dynamics, especially the demand for talented workers. Extant literature has shown that leaders enact various leadership styles such as autocratic leadership, bureaucratic leadership, coach-style leadership, democratic leadership, laissez-faire leadership, strategic leadership, transactional leadership and transformational leadership style. Transformational leadership style multifactor leadership that involves influencing or impact followers (McCleskey, 2014; Nguyen et al., 2017). It enables a leader to articulate a compelling vision and, through charisma and moral appeal, brings social change such as institutional reforms (Ghasabeth, Soosay, & Reaiche, 2015).

Transformational leadership style has five facets of idealized influence attributed, idealized influence behaviour, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration. Individualized consideration demonstrates a leader's ability to pay individualized attention to respective member. This study assessed the influence of individualized consideration relates to talent management practices in the insurance industry in Kenya. The insurance industry is a critical sector that provides insurance covers against various risks such as property damage, medical insurance cover, life assurance covers, and employment. Insurance companies play a significant role globally in providing insurance covers that protect against different risks (Al-Haraisa et al., 2021). However, insurance companies face various challenges such as competition for talent, new technologies, social changes, political changes, and economic changes. The industry has, therefore, depended on developing strategies to compete for a finite and shrinking pool of talented workers (Kajwang, 2022; Kim et al., 2018; Arrawatia & Dixit, 2017). Talent management practices are seen as an essential strategy to improve employee engagement and satisfaction, which can positively impact organizational performance (Dixit & Arrawatia, 2018; King & Vaiman, 2019). Talent management practices focus on improving the competencies of a selected pool of employees with the potential to enable an organization to meet its goals competitively (McDonnell et al., 2017).

In the United States of America, insurance companies have prioritized new markets and digitization over talent management practices (Catlin et al., 2020). This approach has led to over 43 percent of insurance companies experiencing challenges in talent recruitment, forcing them to hire from outside the industry at a higher cost (Shaw, 2021). Similarly, the United Kingdom's insurance industry is complacent regarding talent attraction and retention, with only 28 percent of employees having the necessary digital technology needed to transform the industry, despite the industry depending on technology to distribute its products (Welchman et al., 2022).

In Poland and Lithuania's life insurance industry, talent management practices were found to have an impact on insurance agent performance, with individual competencies being a critical factor (Janowski & Przekota, 2020). In the Nordic insurance industry, a significant challenge was a lack of talent due to global competition for talented workers, the exiting of the older generation from the industry, and the industry not being considered attractive by the young generation (Johannsdottir et al., 2014). In Australia, the insurance industry is experiencing talent challenges, particularly in digital technology, which has compelled insurance companies to pay a high premium to attract and retain talent (Wood, 2021). In China, the talent shortage is experienced across all sectors, including insurance, due to the exiting aging workforce and the shrinking skills in insurance, finance, and information technology (Wang & Sun, 2018). The major problem in Japan is not the lack of talent but how to identify specific talents (Nobutaka, 2021). In less developed jurisdictions such as India, dissatisfaction, lack of clear job roles, and inadequate compensation are significant challenges in the insurance industry (Yadav, 2019).

Therefore, to remain competitive and sustainable, insurance industry leaders should pay more attention to human resources, which is seen as a critical organizational resource. Talent management practices are essential strategies that can improve employee engagement and satisfaction, which can positively impact organizational performance (Al Aina & Atan, 2020). Organizational strategies such as delegation, communication, and talent development can help reduce costs associated with talent turnover.

Individualized consideration (IC) is one of the five dimensions of transformational leadership style (TLS) and is defined as a leader's ability to pay individualized attention to respective members (McCleskey, 2014; Nguyen et al., 2017; Afsar et al., 2017; Batista-Foguet et al., 2021). Transformational leaders who demonstrate IC are able to provide individualized support and guidance to their followers, which can lead to positive outcomes such as talent retention (Edirisooriya, 2020) and improved job satisfaction and individual performance (Braun et al., 2013). Research has shown that IC has a positive impact on talent management practices. For example, in South Africa, Mangisa, Schultz, and Van Hoek (2020) found that transformational leadership style positively influences talent acquisition and talent retention, with IC being one of the key components. Similarly, Edirisooriya (2020) found that IC, along with other transformational leadership dimensions, positively impacts talent retention in Sri Lanka. Overall, IC is an important aspect of transformational leadership style and has been shown to positively impact talent management practices, specifically talent retention. This study therefore sought to assess how the individualized consideration relates to talent management practices in the insurance industry in Kenya.

2. Statement of the Problem

Searching for talented workers to help insurance organizations navigate a complex and competitive business environment is a significant leader challenge (Al-Haraisa et al., 2021). Kenya is no exempt. For instance, despite legal, regulatory and technological investments, Kenya's insurance industry is still faced with insufficient talent attraction, talent retention, compliance with industry regulatory requirements, lack of products diversification, poor customer service, fraud and low insurance penetration rate at 2.4 percent compared to 17 percent in South Africa (IRA, 2019; Kigo & Gachunga, 2016; Azegele et al., 2021; Cytton, 2021; PwC, 2020; Njuguna & Waithaka, 2020; Deloitte, 2020).

Moreover, studies carried out in Kenya have shown that the insurance industry continues to experience various talent management challenges. For example, the industry has a high employees' turnover (Azinga et al., 2019), a lack of critical talent pool (Deloitte, 2019), inadequate involvement of employees in decision making (Munge & Kitiabi, 2017), low investment in employee career development (Kigo & Gachunga, 2016), and a lack of strategic leadership (Otwori & Muturi, 2019).

From the extant literature, there is a conceptual gap where talent management dimensions have been conceptualized differently as an outcome of individualized consideration in the insurance industry in Kenya (Nyokabi et al., 2017; Barasa & Kariuki, 2020; Njiiri et al., 2021). Individualized consideration involves leaders paying attention to the unique needs and development of their employees (Bass & Riggio, 2006). There is limited literature at the international and regional level on the relationship between the individualized considerations and talent management practices. Moreover, according to this researcher, none that exist has been conducted within the Kenya context, explicitly covering the insurance industry. While many variables have contributed to the gaps identified in the literature, the fundamental direction of this study was to bridge the gap by examining the relationship between individualized considerations and talent management practices in Kenya's insurance industry.

3. Objective of the Study

The objective of the study is to assess how individualized consideration influences talent management practices in the insurance industry in Kenya.

4. Research Hypothesis

It was hypothesised that:

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between individualized consideration and talent management.

Ha₁: There is significant relationship between individualized consideration and talent management.

4. Literature Review

4.1. Individualization Consideration

Individualized consideration refers to how a leader appreciates the individual needs of every member of the team (Mir et al., 2020). As observed by Northouse (2022) and Mhatre and Riggio (2014), a leader who enacts individualized consideration behaviour provides a supportive climate and listens to the needs of individual members. Through individualized consideration, leaders train followers to engender fully, take care of the members' interests and be open to followers' needs (Northouse, 2022; Khan et al., 2016; Negussie & Demissie, 2013). As such, individualized consideration enables leaders to support and develop specific members' learning opportunities and to willingly coach and mentor members.

Teymournejad and Elghaei (2017) and Anthony (2017) have argued that a leader's coaching and mentorship process is through a structured and unscheduled conversation, work delegation and autonomy. Expanding on coaching and mentorship, Neupane (2015) postulates that leaders involved in coaching ensure individual needs are marked, a coaching plan developed and the leader continuously provides feedback, which ultimately enables

employees to attain adequate skills, knowledge and attitudes. Mentorship focuses on guiding less experienced follower. Here, Arshad et al. (2021) postulate that mentorship allows a mentee to interact with the mentor, who then offers the mentee an opportunity to meet with other organization members, thus, making learning much more manageable.

Several studies on transformational leadership style suggest that individualized consideration behaviour has contributed to talent management practices, such as talent retention, job satisfaction and employee performance (Long, Yusof, Kowang & Heng, 2014; Mir et al., 2020). For example, Mir et al. (2020) examined talent retention as an emerging business concern. The objective of the study was to identify the factors that mediate between the transformational leader and workers' retention in the banking sector in Pakistan. The study revealed that individualized consideration positively mediated job satisfaction, psychological ownership and talent retention. The study emphasised the need for banking sector managers to improve talent retention by helping employees to appreciate their jobs through psychological ownership.

4.2. Talent Management Practices

Talent management practices have been a concern for practitioners and scholars (Al Aina & Atan, 2020). Talent management has traces in the 1860s, but it was not until the 1990s that McKinsey Group came up with the phrase "war for talent" (Al Aina & Atan, 2020). Despite the lack of a universal definition of talent management, its usage depends on the context (Al Aina & Atan, 2020). The concept is not consistent since each company has a different purpose for talent management (Guerci & Solari, 2012), and the term is interchangeably used to describe processes and outcomes (Salih & Alnaji, 2014). Talent management practices increase the value of human capital, and the aim is to retain employees who are considered talented (Jyoti & Rani, 2014; Isa & Ibrahim, 2014). Various scholars present divergent views on the dimensions of talent management practices (Ebrahim et al., 2021; Bibi, 2018; Rabbi et al., 2015; Ibidunni et al., 2016; Salau et al., 2018; Lyria et al., 2017; Dagogo & Ogechi, 2020).

Talent management practices are how an organization attracts, hires, develops, and retains the best people to hold strategic positions (Dessler, 2013). The essence of talent management practices is to create value for the organization by using internal talent to implement strategies to attain economic value in a competitive market (Jyoti & Rani, 2014; Pandey, 2017; Sparrow & Makram, 2015). Talent management practices, such as employer branding, reward, and development, can improve retention and competitiveness (Sheehan et al., 2018; Isa et al., 2018). The study will discuss talent management as multiple practices adopted by an organization to identify a pool of talented human resources to hold strategic positions for competitive advantage, operationalized through talent acquisition, talent development, talent engagement, and talent retention.

5. Theoretical Framework

5.1. Transformational Leadership Theory

Transformational leadership theorists believe that leaders inspire and motivate individuals to perform tasks that bring out the best of them and the whole team instead of self-interest (Northouse, 2022). The theory of transformational and transactional leadership was first introduced by Burns in 1978 and later developed by Bass in the 1980s (Kumar, 2018; Choi et al., 2016; Tengji et al., 2017; Ahmad et al., 2017). Burns argued that a transformational leader uplifts the morale of the followers and motivates them to enthusiastically carry out the common task for the good of all, while a transactional leader focuses mainly on follower's interests (Burns, 1978, as cited in Yukl, 2013). Bass disputed Burns's transformational and transactional leadership continuum arguments by postulating that influential leaders should apply transformational and transactional behaviours (Bass, 1985, as cited in Northouse, 2019; Kittikunchotiwut, 2019; Choi et al., 2016; Tafvelin, 2013).

Critiques of the transformational leadership theory have argued that it has not received sufficient qualitative research to expound on how it influences followers' feelings and optimism or how it increases followers' commitment to tasks (Northouse, 2022; Yulk, 2013). Odumeru and Ifeanyi (2013) maintain that the theory has relied only on the positive outcomes to businesses but ignored the negative effects it may have on employees such

as stress. Nonetheless, the choice of transformational leadership theory is informed by its association with various positive outcomes, making it essential to this study. Transformational leadership behaviours have positively impacted talent management variables such as employee engagement, job satisfaction, development, retention, and job performance (Osborne & Hammoud, 2017; Chianga & Lin, 2016; Karuri & Nahashon, 2015). Li et al. (2019) used transformational leadership theory to examine the effect of transformational leadership on employee innovation and work behaviour of multinational companies operating in China. Findings from the study indicated that transformational leadership sub-variables, such as trust, positively impact the engagement of employees to work. This theory was deemed relevant in supporting this study in relation to transformational leadership.

Conceptual Framework

6. Research Methodology

Research philosophy is about the nature, source and development of knowledge (Hughes & Sharrock, 2016). The choice of pragmatism is informed by its ontology perspective, which accommodates multiple views, and the epistemology perspective, which allows subjective interpretation of the phenomenon under investigation (Al-Ababneh, 2020). Research design is the researcher's strategy for collecting and analysing data to respond to research objectives (Kothari & Garg, 2014). This study adopted convergent parallel mixed methods because the design ability to collect both qualitative and quantitative data at the same time (Creswell, 2015). This was important in this study since it was aligned with the study pragmatism and also provided in depth understanding on how deployment of transformational leadership style affects talent management practices.

The target population was 2,832 senior management, mid-level management, and lower management of the 56 insurance companies legally operating in Kenya (IRA, 2021). The sample size of 384 was arrived at using Fisher

(1998, as cited in Jung, 2014) formula. A stratified proportionate random approach was applied to generate and arrive at the final sample from three strata of senior management, mid-level management, and lower management. The study used primary quantitative as well as primary qualitative data which was considered has information collected for the first time and not used in any other study before (Kumar, 2018; Johnston, 2014). This study collected data through a self-administered questionnaire. The questionnaire contained both open and closed-ended questions. To ensure the instrument is devoid of any ambiguities, pre-testing was done by submitting it to five experts in leadership and human resources management and their feedback was incorporated.

Descriptive statistics were used to summarize data and make general observations about the data on the relationship between transformational leadership style, and talent management practices in insurance industry in Kenya and the moderating role of organizational culture. Inferential data analysis was conducted by use of regression analysis and Pearson correlation coefficient analysis.

7. Research Findings

The sample size for the study was 384 senior, middle and lower management staff from 56 insurance companies legally operating in Kenya. The selected sample was issued with questionnaires. The returned questionnaires were cross-checked for accuracy and completeness and 299 were found to be valid and reliable and could be used for further analysis and reporting. The returned questionnaires formed a response rate of 77.9%. As explained by Sekaran and Bougie (2016), a response rate of 50% and above is adequate for analysis, 60% and above is good while that of 70% and above is excellent. The response rate of 77.9%, therefore, was excellent for further analysis and reporting the findings of this study.

7.1. Descriptive Analysis Results

Respondents were required to indicate the attribute that best described their immediate supervisors in a five-point scale where 1 represented not at all, 2 once in a while, 3 sometimes, 4 fairly often and 5 frequently.

7.2. Descriptive Analysis for Individualization Consideration

The first objective of the study was to assess how the individualized consideration relates to talent management practices. Respondents were, therefore, requested to give their feeling regarding their immediate supervisors' individualized consideration. The findings obtained were summarized using means and standard deviations presented in Table 1 below. The aggregate mean of 3.45 suggests that immediate supervisors of respondents in the insurance companies in Kenya sometimes intellectually stimulated their employees. This is seen by specific findings where respondents indicated that their supervisors fairly often helped them to develop their abilities (M= 3.70, SD= 1.148); and that they considered difference needs, abilities and aspirations from others (M= 3.51, SD= 1.091). They also indicated that sometimes, their supervisors treated them as individuals not just as members of a team (M= 3.36, SD= 1.255); and supervisors spent most of their time coaching and mentoring them (M= 3.24, SD= 1.090).

Based on these findings, one can conclude that these supervisors appreciated the individual needs of every member of their team, an attribute supported by Northouse (2019) and Mhatre and Riggio (2014) who observe that a leader who enacts individualized consideration behaviour provides a supportive climate and listens to the needs of individual members. Individualized consideration has also been shown to enable leaders to support and develop specific members' learning opportunities and willingly coach and mentor members. These findings agree with those of Long et al. (2014) that leaders should pay more attention to individual employee needs in order to attain motivation and satisfaction in the workplace. The findings also agree with Edirisooriya (2020) who finds that to attain high retention and improved productivity, managers need to understand and actively diagnose the development needs of their employees. Similarly, the findings confirm with Transformational leadership theorists, Bass, who in the 1980s postulated that leaders inspire and motivate their followers to perform tasks that bring out the best of individuals and the whole team, instead of self-interest.

Table 1: Descriptive Analysis for Individualization Consideration

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
My supervisor helps me to develop my abilities.	299	3.70	1.148
My supervisor considers difference needs, abilities, and aspirations from others.	299	3.51	1.091
My supervisor treated me as an individual not just like a member of the team.	299	3.36	1.255
My supervisor spends most of the time coaching and mentoring us.	299	3.24	1.090
Aggregate Score		3.45	1.15

7.3. Descriptive Analysis for Talent Management Practices

The main objective of this study was to examine the relationship between individualized consideration, and talent management practices in insurance industry in Kenya while interrogating the moderating role of organizational culture in that relationship. Previous sections have focused on individualized consideration and organizational culture. This section focuses on talent management practices.

7.4. Talent Acquisition

Here, respondents were presented with statements on talent acquisition and requested to indicate their extent of agreement or disagreement with them. Table 6 below presents a summary of findings. An aggregate mean of 3.84 showed that the respondents agreed on talent acquisition efforts in their insurance companies. Specifically, respondents agreed that the leadership ensured that: appointed talent is effectively on-boarded ($M= 3.85$, $SD= 1.003$); critical positions are filled by talented employees ($M= 3.84$, $SD= .965$); there are updated workforce plans ($M= 3.84$, $SD= 1.047$); and a strong employer brand is built ($M=3.84$, $SD= 1.015$).

These findings agree with those of Deloitte (2016) who undertook a survey of human capital and found that the insurance companies in the past have relied on internal talent. The findings also support the assertion by the National Centre for the Middle Market [NCMM] (2016) that talent acquisition should start with workforce planning. Such a process forms a core business strategy and requires business leaders to carry out an internal assessment of talent status, compare what is within the organization, and develop talent acquisition action plans to bridge the gaps identified. The study also aligns with Rukunga and Nzulwa (2018) and Joseph and Sridevi (2015) who emphasize the need to develop long-term strategies to entice talent to the organization upon identification.

Table 6: Descriptive Analysis for Talent Acquisition

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Leadership ensure appointed talent is effectively on-boarded	299	3.85	1.003
Leadership ensures critical positions are filled by talented employees	299	3.84	.965
Leadership ensures there is updated workforce plans	299	3.84	1.047
Leadership has built a strong employer brand	299	3.84	1.015
Valid N (listwise)		3.84	1.01

7.5. Talent Development

This section presents respondents' extent of agreement or disagreement with statements provided on talent development. The findings are presented in Table 7 below. An aggregate mean of 3.69 suggests that the respondents agreed on average with talent development in their company. The findings specifically show that the respondents agreed, on average, that leadership was aware of and implemented performance management system ($M= 3.86$, $SD= 1.045$); that leadership has developed career development plans ($M= 3.68$, $SD= 1.094$); that there were elaborate learning interventions focused on talent management ($M= 3.61$, $SD= 1.149$); and that leadership ensured succession plan was implemented as core to business strategy ($M= 3.61$, $SD= 1.130$).

The findings align with those of Muyela and Kamaara (2021), who observed that talent development focuses on developing an individual's potential to hold key positions and that it contributes to employees' skills and enhances their ability to take more responsibilities. The findings also agree with Fernandes et al. (2022) that talent management practices, such as development, retention, and reward, positively relate to organizational performance. The study also revealed that talent development was the most critical factor that aids multinational organizational performance, and that organizational culture that supports talent development influenced organizational performance.

Table 7: Descriptive Analysis for Talent Development

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Leadership is aware of and implements performance management system	299	3.86	1.045
Leadership has developed career development plans	299	3.68	1.094
There are elaborate learning interventions focused on talent management	299	3.61	1.149
Leadership ensures succession plan is implemented as core to business strategy	299	3.61	1.130
Aggregate Score		3.69	1.10

7.6. Talent Engagement

This section presents respondents' extent of agreement or disagreement with statements provided in the questionnaire on talent engagement. The summarized findings are presented in Table 8 below. On average, the respondents agreed on talent engagement as shown by an aggregate mean of 3.75. The findings specifically showed that the respondents agreed that leadership provided both team and individualized to employee's support ($M=3.84$, $SD=.951$); that organizational culture is concerned with values, ethics and morals that support both team and individualized success ($M=3.80$, $SD=.984$); that the working environment was flexible to accommodate the changing needs ($M=3.79$, $SD=1.015$); and that there was open and honest conversation across the organization ($M=3.58$, $SD=1.085$).

These findings agree with those of Smythe (2016) who noted that employee engagement as a talent management practice can mitigate costs associated with recruitment, talent retention and talent development, and could assist in organizational change and strategy execution. The finding further aligns with the argument by Lee and Li (2020) that successful talent engagement requires that organizations should pay closer attention to corporate communication, where internal communication is freely and efficiently available to all employees, while providing them with opportunities and resources that can bring change.

Table 8: Descriptive analysis for Talent Engagement

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Leadership provides team, and individual support	299	3.84	.951
Organizational culture is concern with values, ethics, morals that support team and individual success	299	3.80	.984
Working environment is flexible to accommodate changing needs	299	3.79	1.015
There is open and honest conversation across the organization	299	3.58	1.085
Aggregate Score		3.75	1.01

7.7. Talent Retention

This section presents respondents' extent of agreement or disagreement with statements provided on talent retention. Table 9 below presents a summary of the findings obtained. From the findings, the respondents agreed on talent retention in their company as shown by an aggregate mean of 3.57. The findings show that the

respondents agreed, on average, that leadership encouraged and demonstrated working across teams, and individualized support (M= 3.78, SD= 1.064); that leadership ensured that there was adequate workload management across the organization (M= 3.59, SD=1.056); that leadership encouraged and implemented individualized developmental and recognition plans (M= 3.58, SD= 1.103). The respondents were, however, neutral on the statement that there were well-funded reward and recognition programmes specific to talented workforce (M= 3.31, SD= 1.254).

These findings are consistent with those of Vizano et al. (2021) that employees who felt that the organization was providing them with a good reward invest more of their time and efforts in the organization. The findings also agree with the assertion by Bwowe and Marongwe (2018) that a reward system describes organizational policies and procedures on how to recognize employees for their performance. Also supported by these findings is Inegbedion et al. (2020) who find that adequate workload distribution can lead to improved skills and rewards; however, when employees view the same negatively, it can result in low productivity and turnover.

Table 9: Descriptive Analysis for Talent Retention

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Leadership encourages and demonstrates working across teams, and individualized support.	299	3.78	1.064
Leadership ensures there is adequate workload management across the organization.	299	3.59	1.056
Leadership encourages and implements individualized developmental and recognition plans	299	3.58	1.103
There is a well-funded reward and recognition programs specific to talented workforce.	299	3.31	1.254
Aggregate Score		3.57	1.12

7.8. Correlation Analysis

To determine the nature, strength and direction of relationship between study variables, correlation analysis was conducted. From the findings in Table 10, individualized consideration is seen to have a strong positive relationship with talent management practices ($r= 0.552$) Since the p-value (0.000) was less than the selected level of significance (0.05), it was concluded that the relationship between the two variables was significant. Here, if individualized consideration increases, talent management practices will also improve and vice versa. These findings agree with those of Ogola et al. (2017) who found that a positive correlation between individualized consideration and employees' performance at the workplace, and that individualized consideration was about the leader's ability to understand and appreciate individual employees' needs, such as coaching, mentorship and self-development. These findings are also similar to those of Chebon et al. (2019) and Datche and Mukulu (2015) studies in Kenya, which showed that individualized consideration positively affected employee performance and engagement. The findings also confirm Edirisooriya's (2020) finding that individualized consideration had a positive and significant impact on the retention of talented workers.

Table 10: Correlation Analysis

		Talent Management	Individualization Consideration
Talent Management	Pearson Correlation	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	N	299	
Individualization Consideration	Pearson Correlation	.552**	1

	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	299	299

7.9. Test of Hypothesis

The first objective of the study was to assess how the individualized consideration relates to talent management practices. The corresponding hypothesis was;

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between individualized consideration and talent management.

Ha₁: There is significant relationship between individualized consideration and talent management.

Using univariate regression analysis, the study hypothesis was tested. From the model summary findings in Table 11 below, the r-squared for the relationship between individualized consideration and talent management practices was 0.304. This is an indication that at 95% confidence interval, 30.4% variation in talent management practices in insurance industry in Kenya can be attributed to changes in individualized consideration. Individualized consideration can, therefore, be used to explain 30.4% change in talent management practices in insurance industry in Kenya. The remaining 69.6% variation in talent management practices, however, suggests that there are other factors other than individualized consideration that explains talent management practices in insurance industry in Kenya.

Table 11: Model Summary for the Individualization Consideration on Talent Management

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.552 ^a	.304	.302	.66699

a. Predictors: (Constant), Individualization Consideration

The analysis of variance was used to determine whether the regression model is a good fit for the data. From the analysis of variance (ANOVA), findings in Table 12, the study found that $\text{Prob} > F_{1,297} = 0.000$ was less than the selected 0.05 level of significance. This suggests that the model as constituted was fit to predict talent management practices in insurance industry in Kenya. Further, the F-calculated, from the table (130.016) was greater than the F-critical, from f-distribution tables (3.873) supporting the findings that individualized consideration can be used to influence adoption of talent management practices in insurance industry in Kenya.

Table 12: ANOVA for Individualization Consideration on Talent Management Practices

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	57.841	1	57.841	130.016	.000 ^b
	Residual	132.129	297	.445		
	Total	189.970	298			

a. Dependent Variable: Talent Management Practices

b. Predictors: (Constant), Individualization Consideration

From the results in table 13, the following regression model was fitted.

$$Y = 2.098 + 0.469 X_1$$

(X_1 is Individualization Consideration)

The coefficient results showed that the constant had a coefficient of 2.098, suggesting that if individualized consideration was held constant at zero, talent management practices in insurance industry in Kenya would be at 2.098 units. In addition, results showed that individualized consideration coefficient was 0.469, indicating that a unit increase in individualized consideration would result in a 0.469 improvement in talent management practices in insurance industry in Kenya. It was also noted that the P-value individualized consideration coefficient was 0.000, which is less than the set 0.05 significance level, indicating that intellectual stimulation was significant. Based on these results, the study rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternative that there is a strong, positive and significant relationship between individualized consideration and talent management practices.

Compared with multiple regression results it was established that individualized consideration had a higher effect on talent management practices in insurance industry in Kenya unilaterally (coefficient=0.469) as opposed to when it was combined with other variables (coefficient=0.300). The results suggest that in the presence of idealized influence attribute, idealized influence behaviour, inspirational motivation and intellectual stimulation, the effect of individualized consideration weakens.

These results were explained on the basis of descriptive results, correlation analysis, multiple regression analysis, univariate regression analysis, theoretical literature and the empirical literature review. On the basis of descriptive results, the study noted that on average, immediate supervisors in insurance industry in Kenya fairly often (Mean= 3.45) practiced individualized consideration aspect of transformational leadership style. Here, correlation analysis results showed that individualized consideration had a strong positive relationship with talent management practices. This was also supported by the regression results, which showed that individualized consideration had 30% influence on talent management practices when combined with other transformational leadership style dimensions. On its own, it had a 46.9% influence on talent management practices.

These findings are similar to Chebon et al. (2019) and Datche and Mukulu (2015) studies in Kenya, which showed that individualized consideration positively affects employee performance and engagement. It also agrees with those of Ogola et al. (2017) who found positive correlation between individualized consideration and employees' performance at the workplace. Edirisooriya (2020) had also reported that individualized consideration has a positive and significant impact on the retention of talented workers. The findings suggest that managers need to understand and actively diagnose the development needs of their employees in order also revealed that to attain high retention and improved productivity.

Table 13: Beta Coefficients for Individualization Consideration on Talent Management Practices

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	2.098	.147		14.269	.000
1 Individualization Consideration	.469	.041	.552	11.402	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Talent Management Practices

8. Conclusions

The study findings showed that individualized consideration has positive influence on talent management practices in the insurance industry in Kenya. The influence was found to be significant. This meant that individualized consideration has positive significant influence on talent management practices in the insurance industry in Kenya. The study, therefore, rejects the null hypothesis "H₀₁ and accepts the alternative H_{a5}: that there is significant relationship between individualized consideration and talent management.

9. Recommendations

Leaders are also advised to pay more attention to individual employee needs with the aim of attaining motivation and satisfaction in the workplace. Also, to drive the best performance from the employees, insurers should develop management programmes that recognize the efforts of individual employees, such as providing best-performing employees with bonuses and praise while encouraging them to be creative and innovative. There is also the need for managers to demonstrate the ability to empower employees to be innovative when coming up with solutions to problems.

10. Contributions of the Study to Knowledge

The study contribution to the body of knowledge is bifold, that is, from theoretical and empirical. From a theoretical perspective, the findings underpin the theoretical foundation of the study variables by providing empirical evidence on the suitability of Transformational Leadership Theory, Leader-Member Exchange Theory, Human Capital Theory, Resource-Based View, and Competing Value Frame Work in the context of insurance companies in Kenya. The study also contributed to better understanding of distinctive and jointly roles that the five dimensions of the Transformational Leadership style play in talent acquisition, development, engagement and retention.

With regard to empirical contributions, the study has added to the literature that links the transformational leadership style variable with all dimensions of talent management practices. From extant literature, major studies concentrated more on talent turnover, job satisfaction and less focus on talent management practices. This study has, therefore, contributed to the body of knowledge by demonstrating the relationship between transformational leadership style and talent management practices.

11. Suggestions for further research

The focus of this study was on insurance companies, meaning that the findings cannot be applied in other companies. The study, thus, suggests the replication of the same in other sectors, such as banking, to facilitate comparison and generalization of the findings.

This study was limited to transformational leadership style. There is, therefore, a need for other studies to focus on other leadership styles such as servant leadership, authentic leadership and leader-member exchange. Further research should be conducted on the influence of transformational leadership style on talent management practices' specific dimensions such as employee performance. Moreover, future could analyse whether our results are reproducible in individualistic cultures as compared to collectivistic cultures where social relationships are not crucial towards organizational success.

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